

A Roadmap for Open Education in Switzerland: First Steps

Introduction	2
Open Education Global Submission : Une feuille de route collaborative, transcontinentale, pour étendre l'éducation ouverte et libre par un dialogue pluriel	3
Swiss Open Education Day - Submission n° 2: Participatory workshop to draft a roadmap for Open Education in the Swiss Higher Education landscape	7
Swiss Open Education Day - Submission n° 1: A Whitepaper in the form of a wiki: Sharing Open Educational Practices through an Open Educational Resource	8
OER 2022 Submission: A Multilingual Wiki to Leverage Open Culture and Promote Open Educational Practices?	11

Current team members and contributors:

In alphabetic order: Fabio Balli, Barbara Class, Alexandre Enkerli, Sandrine Favre, Denis Gillet, Iris Hensler, Thomas Hervé Mboa Nkoudou, Michele Notari, Guillaume Tschupp.

February 2022

Introduction

During the Spring 2021, a Swiss National Science Foundation Scientific Exchange project to draft a roadmap for Open Education in the Swiss Higher education landscape was accepted, <https://data.snf.ch/grants/grant/205792> .

Supported by the University of Geneva, University of applied sciences and arts Western Switzerland (HEG – HES-SO), EPFL, several universities of teacher education throughout Switzerland (Zurich, Bern, Valais) and by the Open Education Global conference, this exchange explores education as a common good.

Science has been opening up for some years, with visible impact today in terms of commoning (e.g. Open Access, Open Research Data) and fore coming impacts in terms of opening up to diverse knowledge and cultures (UNESCO, 2021). Open movements represent a way to improve efficiency in education and research relying on long-term ecological agendas, particularly in knowledge societies where science and education are deeply entangled.

The overall objective of this scientific exchange is to discuss Open Education (OE) in Switzerland in a constructive dialogue with international experts. The exchange has started informally on-line in September 2021 and will take place physically in Nantes, backed to the Open Education Global conference (May 22-25, 2022), to capitalise on the presence of international experts.

Three specific goals guide the exchange. The first is to **identify key stakeholders who will act as change agents**. The second is to **draft a roadmap** on the basis of a critical analysis of relevant OE expert knowledge. The third consists in **starting a Swiss OE network** for the mutualisation of future actions.

Work conducted within the current team is visible in four recent submissions made to three conferences:

- Open Education (OER) Conference, London, 26-28 April, <https://www.alt.ac.uk/events/open-education-conference>
- Swiss Open Education day, Bern, 14 May, <https://openeducationday.ch/fr/> (2 soumissions)
- Open Education Global, Nantes, 23-25 May, <https://conference.oeglobal.org/2021/in-person-congress/>

And a white paper on Open Educational Practices, in the form of a wiki that is in the making: https://houseofcommons.ch/wiki/index.php?title=Open_Education . You are cordially invited to **contribute** to this wiki - to do so click on *Request account* on the top right and you will be able to edit and add pages in the following minutes.

To get in touch, please write to Barbara.Class@unige.ch or to any other team member.

Open Education Global Submission : Une feuille de route collaborative, transcontinentale, pour étendre l'éducation ouverte et libre par un dialogue pluriel

Inspiré par la science ouverte (UNESCO 2021), notre groupe transcontinental élabore une feuille de route collaborative pour étendre l'éducation ouverte et libre (EOL) par un dialogue ouvert à différents systèmes de connaissances et à diverses épistémologies. Ce laboratoire d'apprentissage vise un exercice d'idéation pour ouvrir des « voies de transition » vers une EOL étendue, au-delà des ressources éducatives libres (REL) et de leurs dimensions techniques.

Malgré des périodes de contrôle autoritaire, l'histoire révèle des cycles d'ouverture progressive (Peter et Deimann 2013). Dans ce foisonnement où beaucoup ont voix, nous voulons favoriser une écoute active équitable pour pérenniser cette ouverture en favorisant la diversité épistémique et les communs éducationnels.

Depuis des décennies, la pédagogie ouverte remet en question la prérogative de décider de ce qui constitue une connaissance à enseigner (Paquette 1976). Au début de cette Décennie des langues autochtones (UNESCO 2020) et dans un contexte de décolonisation des savoirs (Santos 2021), une démarche visant la justice épistémique et l'équité pédagogique se doit d'accorder une place de choix à la diversité des savoirs.

La littérature sur l'EOL aborde divers enjeux depuis le Nord mondialisé: pratiques et ressources éducatives libres, certification, CLOM... (Baker 2017; Blessinger et Bliss 2016; Clinton-Lisell 2021; Cronin et Maclaren 2018; Ehrenreich et al. 2020; Gunness et al. 2021; Hylén et al. 2012; Jeong 2019; Peter et Deimann 2013; Weller 2014; Weller 2020). Aujourd'hui encore, les REL sont majoritairement créées en anglais dans le Nord mondialisé (de los Arcos et Weller 2018). Ces portes d'entrée vers l'EOL, pour lesquelles l'UNESCO a fait une recommandation spécifique (UNESCO 2019), valorisent peu la richesse de langues et pratiques culturelles diverses.

Selon Wildavsky (2015) les CLOM sont surtout réalisés dans une optique de consommation et ont peu de pertinence en dehors de l'hémisphère nord. Si l'adaptation (traduction, révision, remixage...) permet la contextualisation des REL (Wiley 2014, cité dans Wolfenden et Adinolfi 2019), la localisation est une pratique sociale plus profonde, dans laquelle la compétence découle d'une interdépendance entre les contributions et l'agentivité des individus et du collectif (Priestley et al 2015 cité dans Wolfenden et Adinolfi 2019). Par ailleurs, le respect des connaissances traditionnelles peut avoir d'importantes conséquences sur l'usage de ressources provenant de contextes locaux. Les étiquettes de savoirs traditionnels (Local Contexts s.d.) encadrent et spécifient des restrictions à cet égard.

Au sein de la communauté d'OEGlobal 2022, nous souhaitons ouvrir la porte à une co-conception large, selon une approche tirée de la science ouverte qui encourage le multilinguisme et la diversité épistémique. Nous avons déjà formé un groupe dont les membres se trouvent à des points distincts de la planète : Cameroun, Canada et Suisse (romande et allemande).

Selon nous, l'EOL s'est construite dans un champ de tension entre liberté et transparence d'un côté et contrôle de l'autre (Baker 2017). Tisser des fils solides d'EOL dans la trame de l'éducation supérieure en place pourrait produire une toile intéressante. En réalité, ces fils brodent déjà un vaste réseau qui mérite d'être renforcé. Nous pensons entre autres à Corinne Pelluchon (2021), Boaventura de Sousa Santos (2021), Vinciane Despret (2021), Florence Piron (2017) ou Bruno Latour (2006), toujours dans

le Nord mondialisé mais avec des mains tendues pour comprendre et travailler en bonne intelligence avec d'autres systèmes de production de connaissances.

Loin de se limiter à la technologie, l'EOL est d'abord et avant tout une affaire de valeurs, d'épistémologies, de pratiques concertées et efficaces ainsi que d'une capacité à la remise en question. Les valeurs fréquemment citées sont la liberté, la justice, le respect, l'ouverture en tant qu'attitude ou culture, l'absence d'obstacles, la promotion du partage, l'accessibilité, la transparence, la collaboration, l'agentivité, l'auto-direction, la personnalisation et la participation universelle. Comment amorcer ce chantier en incluant les systèmes de savoirs et de connaissances de façon maximale ? Comme pour la science ouverte, il existe de nombreuses « voies de transition » vers l'EOL. L'élaboration collaborative d'une feuille de route soutient un principe de flexibilité épistémique.

Dans le cadre d'un groupe de travail international, initié par l'obtention d'un financement « échange scientifique » du Fonds National Suisse et intitulé *A Roadmap for Open Education in Switzerland: First Steps*, nous travaillons depuis le mois de septembre 2021 sur plusieurs axes. Le premier axe consiste à interroger des spécialistes EOL, dans une approche de type Delphi, pour faire émerger le savoir tacite en la matière. Le deuxième axe consiste à travailler au niveau de la pratique enseignante et à mettre en place un livre blanc sur les pratiques éducatives libres sous forme d'un wiki participatif qui implique diverses personnes.

La méthode Delphi (référence aux orateurs de Delphe) a pour objectif d'interroger des spécialistes d'un domaine afin de bâtir sur leurs prédictions et intuitions et d'arriver à un consensus en plusieurs itérations. Durant le Swiss Open Education Day (14 mai 2022), l'objectif est d'atteindre un consensus à l'issue d'une première itération sur les différentes dimensions de l'EOL - définition, épistémologie, économie, légale, recherche, etc. Notre atelier OEGlobal 2022 invitera les gens à se prononcer sur ces résultats vers une deuxième itération visant un nouveau consensus.

Durant cet atelier, nous souhaitons profiter de la participation internationale de spécialistes de l'EOL pour poursuivre le travail vers un troisième axe: une feuille de route transcontinentale tracée par la participation extensive. Les personnes qui participeront à ce laboratoire d'apprentissage seront invitées à définir les sujets pertinents et les moyens d'établir la feuille de route collaborative en donnant la priorité à leurs attentes (augmenter les données de l'étude Delphi, contribuer au wiki, suggérer des axes à développer...).

Ce laboratoire d'apprentissage aspire à une collaboration accrue entre diverses parties prenantes. Pour ce faire, nous procéderons à un remue-méninge à partir des enjeux soulevés par l'étude Delphi et par des contributions externes ou internes au groupe. L'approche privilégiée pour la facilitation de ce laboratoire s'inspire d'une démarche d'idéation en co-conception d'expériences d'apprentissage.

Références

- Baker FW. (2017, 2017/03/01). An Alternative Approach: Openness in Education Over the Last 100 Years. *TechTrends*, 61(2), 130-140. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11528-016-0095-7>
- Blessinger P, Bliss TJ. (dir.). (2016). *Open Education. International Perspectives in Higher Education*. Open Book Publishers. <https://www.openbookpublishers.com/product/577>
- Clinton-Lisell V. (2021). Open Pedagogy: A Systematic Review of Empirical Findings. *Journal of Learning for Development*, 8(2), 255-268. <https://jl4d.org/index.php/ejl4d/article/view/511>

- Cronin CMG, Maclaren I. (2018). Conceptualising OEP: A review of theoretical and empirical literature in Open Educational Practices. *Open Praxis*, 10, 127-143.
<https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1177676.pdf>
- de los Arcos, B, Weller M. (2018). *A Tale of Two Globes: Exploring the North/South Divide in Engagement with Open Educational Resources* (J. Schöpfel & U. Herb, Hrsg.; S. 147–155). Litwin Books. <http://litwinbooks.com/open-divide.php>
- Despret V. (2021). *Autobiographie d'un poulpe et autres récits d'anticipation*. Actes Sud Nature, Mondes sauvages. <https://www.actes-sud.fr/catalogue/nature-et-environnement/autobiographie-dun-poulpe>
- Ehrenreich J, Mazar I, Rampelt F, Schunemann I, Sood I. (2020). *Recognition and Verification of Credentials in Open Education – OEPASS*. <https://oepass.eu/outputs/io3/>
- Gunness S, Tarling I, Haiping E. (2021). Gathering Expert Opinions on Self-directed Learning and Online Assessment Using OER—A Delphi Approach for Redesigning Student Assessments. Dans D. Burgos et J. Olivier (dir.), *Radical Solutions for Education in Africa: Open Education and Self-directed Learning in the Continent* (p. 59-86). Springer Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-4099-5_4
- Hylén J, van Damme D, Mulder F, D'Antoni S. (2012). *Open Educational Resources: Analysis of Responses to the OECD Country Questionnaire*. OECD. <https://doi.org/10.1787/5k990rjhvtlv-en>
- Jeong H. (2019). Rethinking Open Universities: What Makes Them Unique? *International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 20(4), 152-166.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.19173/irrodl.v20i4.4163>
- Latour B. (2006). *Nous n'avons jamais été modernes: Essai d'anthropologie symétrique*. La Découverte. https://www.editions-ladecouverte.fr/nous_n_avons_jamais_ete_modernes-9782707148490
- Local Contexts (s.d.). TK labels. <https://localcontexts.org/labels/traditional-knowledge-labels/>
- Paquette C. (1976). *Vers une pratique de la pédagogie ouverte*. Éditions NHP.
- Pelluchon C. (2021). *Les Lumières à l'âge du vivant*. Seuil.
- Peter S, Deimann M. (2013). On the role of openness in education: A historical reconstruction. *Open Praxis*, 5(1), 7-14. <https://journals.openedition.org/dms/2491>
- Priestley M, Biesta GJJ, Robinson S. (2015). Teacher agency: what is it and why does it matter? In R Kneyber & J Evers (eds.), *Flip the System: Changing Education from the Bottom Up*. London: Routledge <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315678573-15>
- Piron F, Diouf A, Dibounje Madiba M., Mboa Nkoudou T, Aubierge Ouangré Z, Tessy D, Achaffert H, Anderson P, Lir Z. (2017). Le libre accès vu d'Afrique francophone subsaharienne. *Revue française des sciences de l'information et de la communication*.
<https://doi.org/10.4000/rfsic.3292>
- Santos BdS. (2021). *Decolonising the University : the Challenge of Deep Cognitive Justice*. Cambridge Scholars Publishing. <https://www.cambridgescholars.com/product/978-1-5275-0003-7>
- UNESCO (2019). *Recommandation de l'UNESCO sur les REL*.
<https://fr.unesco.org/themes/building-knowledge-societies/oer/recommandation>

- UNESCO. (2020) *La Décennie des langues autochtones 2022-2032 sera axée sur les droits fondamentaux de leurs utilisateurs*. <https://fr.unesco.org/news/decennie-langues-autochtones-2022-2032-sera-axee-droits-fondamentaux-leurs-utilisateurs>
- UNESCO. (2021). *Recommandation de l'UNESCO sur une science ouverte*. https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000379949_fre
- Weller M. (2014). *The Battle for Open: How Openness Won and Why it Doesn't Feel Like Victory*. Ubiquity Press. <https://doi.org/10.5334/bam>
- Weller M. (2020). Open and Free Access to Education for All. Dans D. Burgos (dir.), *Radical Solutions and Open Science: An Open Approach to Boost Higher Education* (p. 1-15). Springer Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-4276-3_1
- Wiley D. (2014). *The Access Compromise and the 5th R*. <https://opencontent.org/blog/archives/3221>.
- Wildavsky B. (2015). MOOCs in the developing world: Hope or hype? *International Higher Education*, 80, 23-25. <https://doi.org/10.6017/ihe.2015.80.6154>
- Wolfenden F, Adinolfi L. (2019). An exploration of agency in the localisation of open educational resources for teacher development. *Learning, Media and Technology*, 44(3), 327–344. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17439884.2019.1628046>

Swiss Open Education Day - Submission n° 2: Participatory workshop to draft a roadmap for Open Education in the Swiss Higher Education landscape

Open movements improve education and research relying on long-term ecological agendas, particularly in knowledge societies where science and education are deeply entangled. Through a SNSF supported scientific exchange, *A Roadmap for Open Education in Switzerland: First Steps*, running September 2021-July 2022, we have 3 specific goals. The first is to identify key stakeholders who are ready to act as change agents in Switzerland. The second is to draft a roadmap on the basis of a critical analysis of relevant Open Education (OE) expert knowledge (Delphi study). The third consists in starting a Swiss Open Education network for the mutualisation of future actions.

Policy support towards OE at federal, cantonal, institutional and individual levels are needed to support practice where a myriad of initiatives have been conducted for several decades (e.g. EduTechWiki, <https://edutechwiki.unige.ch/> ; Promotion for open source software, <https://www.ch-open.ch/>). The federal message on the support of Education, Research and Innovation¹ is an important decision instrument that sets the direction every 4 years. Discussions for the 2025-2028 period have started and heading towards Openness in Education and increased Openness in Science is desirable. Policy gives the orientation and then it is institutions' and practitioners' role to find creative ways to operationalise these orientations into everyday practice. This is the reason why the Delphi study addressed different topics in addition to policy: defining OE, philosophy, epistemology, values, stakeholders, economic, legal and technological issues.

This session is organised as a 90 mn workshop. First a short presentation will explain how the Delphi study functions. Participants will then work in groups on one of the above-mentioned topics or suggest a new topic that is considered of foremost importance and directly related to designing directions for OE (e.g. OER; AI; sustainability). Working with collected data from Swiss and international OE stakeholders, each group will produce a common understanding for the topic.

Time management:

- Before the workshop: introduce yourself on this padlet https://padlet.com/barbara_class/nw29kdzvs92dvlht
- During the workshop: process data from the Delphi study that is available from <https://tecfa.unige.ch/perso/class/CH-OE-2022/> ; write the suggested common understanding on this padlet: https://padlet.com/barbara_class/k2hddyblqwfi47q1
- After the workshop: if you are interested to be involved in the Swiss OE project, stay connected. Together and with the support of OE CH organisers brainstorm ways to capitalise on this workshop activity.

¹ Federal message on the support of Education, Research and Innovation for the 2021-2024 period: <https://www.fedlex.admin.ch/eli/fga/2020/866/fr>

Swiss Open Education Day - Submission n° 1: A Whitepaper in the form of a wiki: Sharing Open Educational Practices through an Open Educational Resource

Open Education (OE) is an umbrella term organised around values of sharing, traceability, respect, liberty, equal access, agency, justice and empowerment. It aims at broadening knowledge and making it more accessible by encouraging participatory approaches and removing barriers. It relies on group and community capacities, and invites learners to have “*an active, constructive engagement with content, tools and services*” (Geser, 2007, p. 37), fostering self-management, creativity and teamwork. While higher education institutions are increasingly adopting Open Science following UNESCO recommendations (1999, 2018, 2021), leveraging Open Education still affords deeper engagement through widespread collaboration. Our multinational team is creating a whitepaper around Open Educational Practices (OEP) to foster the adoption of an open culture across scholars’ and learners’ communities. .

Using a transcontinental collaborative approach, we are in the process of designing a whitepaper aimed at scholars interested in teaching beyond academic boundaries, in an open ecosystem, i.e. cross-fertilisation of knowledge commons, Open Science, Open Data, Open Library, Open culture, Citizen’s science, Open source software and hardware.

Adopting means aligned with our values, we use a multilingual, libre and open-source MediaWiki to foster open collaboration around this endeavour and conceive the whitepaper as an Open Education Resource (OER), https://houseofcommons.ch/wiki/index.php?title=Open_Education

The team starts with a majority of higher education, French-speaking scholars from Switzerland, Canada and Cameroon with a clear intention to broaden collaboration across languages and regions.

Building on our field experience, we aim to find contextual answers to questions such as: How might we find common ground on what qualifies as Open Educational Practices? How can we open learning to a diversity of knowledge systems? How can we link constructivism, cognitivism, connectivism, and learning experience design with the help of our pedagogical backgrounds? What is required to contribute to, and maintain OER and other Knowledge Commons?

Several obstacles prevent the use of OEP: discoverability, accessibility, and sustainability of OER (Luo et al., 2020). In addition, the transition from restrictive practices to open-ended practices depends on the threshold phase of integration and reconstruction (Tur et al., 2020). To overcome this phase, we involve scholars as full-fledged wiki stakeholders and aim for the multiplication effect of open practices, sharing experiences with OE, OER and OEP. In doing so, we put together our shared understanding of open ecosystems and then focus primarily on open practices and their practical implementations. Through the multinational team, local and national contexts are considered. Students’ assignments can contribute to this effort, adding learners’ perspective in a purposeful way to promote creativity, deep learning and sustainable resources (Clinton-Lisell, 2021; Werth and Williams, 2021). OERs are improved, adapted, translated through publicly-shared tasks that gain value over time, cohorts, and across languages (Wiley & Hilton, 2018) and this whitepaper is itself conceived as an OER.

References

Clinton-Lisell, V. (2021). Open Pedagogy: A Systematic Review of Empirical Findings. *Journal of Learning for Development*, 8(2), 255-268. <https://jl4d.org/index.php/ejl4d/article/view/511>

Geser, G. (Ed.). (2007). *Open educational practices and resources: OLCOS roadmap 2012*. Salzburg Research & EduMedia Group. http://www.olcos.org/cms/upload/docs/olcos_roadmap.pdf.

Luo, T., Hostetler, K., Freeman, C., & Stefaniak, J. (2020). The power of open: benefits, barriers, and strategies for integration of open educational resources. *Open Learning: The Journal of Open, Distance and e-Learning*, 35(2), 140-158. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02680513.2019.1677222>

Tur, G., Havemann, L., Marsh, D., Keefer, J. M., & Nascimbeni, F. (2020). Becoming an open educator: towards an open threshold framework. *Research in Learning Technology*, 28(0). <https://doi.org/10.25304/rlt.v28.2338>

UNESCO. (2021). *Recommendation on Open Science*. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000379949.locale=en>

Werth, E., & Williams, K. (2021). What Motivates Students About Open Pedagogy? Motivational Regulation Through the Lens of Self-Determination Theory. *International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 22(3).

Biographies

Alex Enkerli is a Technopedagogical Advisor at Collecto, where he helps learning professionals make technology appropriate for their contexts, just like he did as a technopédagogue for Vitrine technologie-éducation from 2014 to 2016. Alex comes back to this role after a stint in Ottawa (creating cybersecurity learning pathways and a Massively Open and Nimble Online Collaborative Learning Experience on Public Engagement in partnership with CSPS, #Learn4PE), and in Saguenay-Lac-Saint-Jean to conduct participatory-action research at CO^{lab}.

Sandrine Favre is a doctoral student and scientific collaborator at the University of Teacher Education in Bern, Switzerland. She is currently working in several working groups on Open Education, including the implementation of an OER Policy within the institution and the Digital Skills Academy project. <https://d-skills.ch/>

Fabio Balli mobilises teams for creation-as-research initiatives based on solidarity, subjectivity and creativity. He authors a research notebook on how open science can foster French-speaking research in Canada (<https://sciencesouvertes.hypotheses.org>). Fabio does research on health commons and collective law-making, at Concordia University (Montreal) and IUC Turin. <https://www.fabioballi.net>

Barbara Class is researcher and senior lecturer at TECFA, the educational technology unit of the Faculty of Psychology and Education Sciences, University of Geneva. Collaborating with Daniel Schneider for more than 20 years paved the way to her current activities in Open Education. More information available from <https://tecfa.unige.ch/perso/class/>

Denis Gillet leads the Interaction Systems Group (REACT) at the Swiss Federal Institute of Technology in Lausanne (EPFL). He is a board member of the EPFL Center for Learning Sciences and the President of the Swiss EdTech Collider, an incubator for startups in educational technologies. He is currently leading the Swiss Digital Skills Academy, an national initiative to promote open educational resources and platforms (<https://d-skills.ch/>).

Guillaume Tschupp is a lecturer at the Haute Ecole Pédagogique du Valais for teacher training. He teaches e-learning, digital education, media education and educational robotics. He is also in charge of e-learning support for the institution and its collaborators. Open education is at the heart of his activity.

Michele Notari is Professor in technology enhanced learning at the University of Teacher Education in Bern Switzerland and the University of Hong Kong. His research area is computer supported collaborative learning, technology enhanced project-based learning, wearable computing, learning using Computer mediated reality and learning design fostering the 21st Century Skills.

Thomas Hervé Mboa Nkoudou is a professor at the "Ecole Supérieure des Sciences et Techniques de l'Information et de la Communication" (ESSTIC) of the University of Yaoundé II in Cameroon. His work focuses on open science, social innovation, peer production and digital humanities.

Iris Henseler Stierlin is the head of the Center for Educational Governance and Democracy at the Zurich University of Teacher Education. She has many years of experience in national and international education, in the economy and in other professional fields. As an organizational developer, her work focuses primarily on the organizational aspects of Open Education.

OER 2022 Submission: A Multilingual Wiki to Leverage Open Culture and Promote Open Educational Practices?

We share a transcontinental collaborative approach to prototyping a whitepaper. It will promote open culture among scholars focused on teaching activities while situating education in a wider “ecosystem of opens”, i.e. science, software, hardware, libraries, data, etc.

We model behaviour through inspiring practices. Since form and process matter, we use a multilingual wiki for our open collaboration. Benefitting from a diverse team with French-speaking members from Switzerland, Cameroon, and Canada, we recently began the prototyping process in French with the aim of federating valuable resources from varied sources. Work in progress available from: https://houseofcommons.ch/wiki/index.php?title=Open_Education

Through our collaboration, we find contextual answers to the field’s broad issues. How might we find common ground on what qualifies as an OEP? What roles do OERs play in our activities? Which trends in the movement towards Open Education provide us with the most fruitful opportunities to overcome barriers to learning? How might we mesh our pedagogical backgrounds, from constructivism and cognitivism to connectivism and learning experience design? These questions highlight OEPs’ diversity and dynamism.

Open pedagogies directly involve learners in their learning experiences. During the learning process, participants are encouraged to have “*an active, constructive engagement with content, tools and services*”, this aims to “*promote learners’ self-management, creativity and working in teams*” (Geser, 2007, p. 37). For instance, instead of “disposable assignments”, practitioners demonstrate creativity, co-designing courses with learners based on values such as mutual respect and trust, deep learning, as well as a willingness to engage in meaningful and sustainable activities (Clinton-Lisell, 2021; Werth and Williams, 2021). Since assignments are shared publicly, they accrue value with time, across cohorts or even across languages. Through continuous assessment, existing OERs are improved, new ones created, others adapted, translated, etc. In the process, participants “learn by doing” in the constructivist sense (Wiley & Hilton, 2018): a win-win situation for responsible actors, aware of the public good and willing to contribute.

Despite the clear benefits of OER and open pedagogies, adoption remains difficult for faculty, students, and institutions (Luo et al., 2020). To become an open educator, several barriers exist, e.g. OER discoverability, accessibility, and sustainability (Luo et al., 2020). Changes in professional practice prove challenging. They touch on identity, inspiring examples become hard to find, creativity is needed, roadmaps are rare, and risk of failure is ever present. Yet what might be deemed a failure often morphs into a valuable learning moment. In view of threshold concepts adapted into threshold practices by Tur et al. (2020), moving from restrictive practices to open-ended ones hinges on the liminal stage of integration and reconstruction.

Involving scholars as full-fledged wiki stakeholders, we aim for the multiplying effect of open practices. Project participants are appropriating and implementing OE, OERs and OEPs in their local and national contexts. We will share our experience, starting from the team’s shared understanding of open ecosystems, to open education with a focus on open practices and their implementation.

References

- Bittner, H., Herbstreit, M., Krause, N., & Lehmann, C. (2018). MOIN. Projects of the BMBF-funding. OERinfo 2017/2018. Special volume of the journal Synergie, 88–95. Retrieved from <https://www.synergie.uni-hamburg.de/media/sonderbaende/sonderband-synergie-oeerinfoprojekte-2017-18-moin.pdf>
- Clinton-Lisell, V. (2021, 07/19). Open Pedagogy: A Systematic Review of Empirical Findings. *Journal of Learning for Development*, 8(2), 255-268. <https://jl4d.org/index.php/ejl4d/article/view/511>
- Cronin, C. M. G. et Maclaren, I. (2018). Conceptualising OEP: A review of theoretical and empirical literature in Open Educational Practices. *Open Praxis*, 10, 127-143.
- Geser, G., Ed. (2007). *Open educational practices and resources: OLCOS roadmap 2012*. Salzburg, Austria: Salzburg Research & EduMedia Group. Retrieved from http://www.olcos.org/cms/upload/docs/olcos_roadmap.pdf
- Hegarty, B. (2015). Attributes of open pedagogy: A model for using open educational resources. *Educational Technology*, LV, 3-12.
- Henriksen, D., Mishra, P., Creely, E. et Henderson, M. (2021, 2021/07/01). The Role of Creative Risk Taking and Productive Failure in Education and Technology Futures. *TechTrends*, 65(4), 602-605. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11528-021-00622-8>
- Luo, T., Hostetler, K., Freeman, C., & Stefaniak, J. (2020). The power of open: benefits, barriers, and strategies for integration of open educational resources. *Open Learning: The Journal of Open, Distance and e-Learning*, 35(2), 140-158. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02680513.2019.1677222>
- Meyer, J., Land, R. et Baillie, C. (2010). *Threshold Concepts and Transformational Learning* (vol. 42). Sense Publishers.
- Tur, G., Havemann, L., Marsh, D., Keefer, J. M. et Nascimbeni, F. (2020, 03/09). Becoming an open educator: towards an open threshold framework. *Research in Learning Technology*, 28(0). <https://doi.org/10.25304/rlt.v28.2338>
- Werth, E. et Williams, K. (2021). What Motivates Students About Open Pedagogy? Motivational Regulation Through the Lens of Self-Determination Theory. *International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 22(3).
- Wiley, D. et Hilton, J. L. (2018). Defining OER-Enabled Pedagogy. *International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 19(4). <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.19173/irrodl.v19i4.3601>